

Requirements for Completion of Initialisation Phase

Version 3, April 2026

1. Purpose

This document serves as a **common framework** for the Initialisation Phase of your basic service. This version 3 of the document applies to all basic services and their initialisation phase proposals as of July 2026. Older basic services follow the instructions in the respective earlier versions of the document¹.

The document describes

- the **service development framework** Base4NFDI expects you to follow in the Initialisation Phase,
- **mandatory deliverables** requested by Base4NFDI,
- **aspects to be considered** for each deliverable,
- the expected **time frame** (in particular looking ahead to the Base4NFDI Integration Phase and the proposal preparation).

The framework is supposed to make sure you follow a **structured approach to service development** by

- performing a requirements analysis,
- evaluating and re-using services and components that could become part of your basic service,
- designing your service based on the requirements,
- developing a minimal viable prototype,
- testing it with first users,
- reaching out to sections and other interested parties and
- documenting the results of these tasks.

It also provides links to useful **guides** supporting each task.

¹ v1: <https://zenodo.org/records/11519611> (Round 1-7), v2: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15020379> (Round 8-11, April 2025-April 2026)

2. Mandatory Deliverables in the Initialisation Phase

There are **seven mandatory deliverables** for the Initialisation Phase, four of them with regard to your documentation of the Initialisation Phase. You were already asked to consider these mandatory requirements when writing your Initialisation Phase proposal: either, by integrating them into your work plan, or by at least mapping your service-specific work program and corresponding deliverables and milestones to them.

At the beginning of the Initialisation Phase, all items of your work plan (e.g. work packages, deliverables, milestones) have been transferred to the Base4NFDI project management software [OpenProject](#) (OP). In addition, the seven mandatory Initialisation Phase deliverables requested by Base4NFDI will be provided as OP tasks as well. During the Initialisation Phase, you must track your progress in [OpenProject](#) and describe all results you accomplish. Utilise the support offered by the Base4NFDI team if you encounter any difficulties (e.g. by contacting the [TA1 team](#) or your [Service Stewards](#)). You should also check out our guide [HowTo: Reporting in Initialisation Phase](#).

Also remember that you might have to prepare your next basic service **proposal for the Integration phase** early during the Initialisation Phase. For the application you need an up-to-date state of at least deliverables D.Ini.1, D.Ini.2, and D.Ini.3 in [OpenProject](#) as early as the deadlines stated in [section 4](#) of this document. Please also note that the **deadlines** for these three deliverables are not mandatory per se: They are set up so that all the documents needed for the Integration Phase proposal are ready when required. This proposal must be submitted six months after the start of the Initialisation Phase if further funding of the service is to be uninterrupted. If this timeline does not fit with your project planning, you can change it. Please mention in your final report why you changed it, and also adapt the dates in your respective [OpenProject](#) tasks.

The following sections describe each mandatory deliverable in detail.

*While the remainder of this document gives detailed instructions on the **mandatory deliverables**, Base4NFDI recommends documenting your own work packages and deliverables just as thoroughly. Link external resources to the work packages and make them publicly accessible where appropriate. Since the basic service development is part of a DFG project, all project results should be made available under respective open licenses, e.g. CC-BY 4.0 and should meet the FAIR principles.*

Deliverable D.Ini.1 Requirements Analysis

- Assess the needs of your community in a two-part **in-depth analysis**:
 - a) What needs are being met by existing services in relation to the proposed basic service (with regard to relevant consortia's working group)? What are the expectations of a basic service? Do already existing specific services need extra support for their users, that can be provided by a basic service?
Present the results to the NFDI section(s) involved (and their corresponding

working groups, if applicable). What issues have the sections/working groups already identified?

b) Bring together all the services in the consortia regarding this topic and explore possible commonalities (in addition to the issues already identified).

Be aware of dependencies between services (user services, basic services), of inconsistencies and blind spots and how this can lead to problems for a basic service. Will a basic service work well within the overall architecture of a consortium?

- Identify **contacts in the consortia** on this issue and, if possible, work together to collect information. Consider both qualitative and quantitative methods. Share your findings.
 - Where appropriate, use surveys (TA4 has already provided you with feedback from the consortia), interviews and/or workshops to gather information and ask [Section Liaison Officers](#), [Section Co-Spokespersons](#) or [Service Stewards](#) about surveys/interviews/workshops that have already taken place. Document your process and/or methodology.
 - Create user stories, epics and/or personas as appropriate.
- **TA1 team** can support this step (requirements analysis and/or its documentation) and the **Service Stewards** can assist by liaising with the consortia and their user bases, and by gathering the needs of the sections and the working groups.
 - TA1 team can support the requirements analysis by offering events (e.g. persona workshops or community meetings).
 - TA1 provides a [Toolkit for Requirements Analysis Strategy](#), a [Persona Creation Kit](#) and a [User Story Guide](#)
- It is recommended that you complete a first draft of your analysis and its documentation (summary of findings and methodology used) within **3 months** of the start date. Please also consider that requirements may change over time or new requirements may come up, e.g. during piloting and testing of your prototype. It is highly recommended to update the requirements documentation when the actual requirements change or new requirements become known.
 - We encourage you to openly publish your survey/interview data and workshop results (e.g. on [Zenodo](#)).
 - We also recommend managing the requirements publicly (where possible) in an environment where they can be discussed, linked to each other or related resources (e.g. tests), prioritized, tagged or otherwise managed.

Deliverable D.Ini.2 Evaluation of Existing Software and Services

- Depending on what type of service you develop, collect possible candidates for your basic service, regarding **existing software solutions, tools, methods and services** available on the market.
 - What software/services on this topic already exist within the consortia? Do they need a basic service? (include TA4 feedback)
- Compare the collected solutions with the requirements (see D.Ini.1) using appropriate **evaluation criteria**.

- Which solutions meet the requirements and to what extent?
- The aim of the comparison is to **identify solutions** for a stable, secure, sustainable and sufficiently scalable basic service.
 - Open licenses are mandatory to ensure transparency and to avoid lock-in scenarios (for services and technologies used).
 - A typical scenario could be to take an existing domain-specific service or a basic service deployed in one or just a few consortia and to promote it as a new basic service for NFDI.
 - Note that all components to be reused and to become part of the basic service, must achieve a [Technology Readiness Level](#) of TRL 3-4 (minimum) already *at the beginning* of the Initialisation Phase.
- The **TA1 team** supports this step (service and software evaluation and/or its documentation) with a [Service Evaluation Guide](#), and by monitoring the service landscape and ensuring that there are no blind spots.
Service Stewards can assist you, in particular by identifying current technology trends within the consortia and their user bases.
- It is recommended that you complete your evaluation and its documentation (summary of findings) within **6 months** of the start date.

Deliverable D.Ini.3 Service Design

- Based on the results of the software and service evaluation (see D.Ini.2), **select your service design** (including tools, frameworks, methods and technologies).
 - The service design includes meeting and, if necessary, improving the requirements for the basic services.
 - The service design also includes the architecture of the basic service (technology, APIs, user experience, training, helpdesk, etc., depending on your type of service)
 - It also includes its connection/interaction with the other basic services and services in the consortia (interfaces, workflows, organisational).
- During development and selection of your components, also keep the **accessibility**², **information security**, and **scalability** of your service in mind right from the start.
- The **TA1 team** supports this step (service design and/or its documentation) to guide you through the process, and by monitoring the service landscape and ensuring that there are no blind spots. For a quick brainstorming on relevant service design aspects use our handout [20 Questions about Service Design](#). To learn more about service design aspects to be addressed in Base4NFDI, take a look into the [Service Design Guide](#).
Service Stewards can assist you, in particular by identifying current technology trends within the consortia and their user bases.
- It is recommended that you complete your service design and its documentation within **6 months** of the start date.

² See also [Barrierefreiheitsstärkungsgesetz](#), in effect from June 2025.

Deliverable D.Ini.4 Service Development as a Prototype

- Service development can include the **development of new software**, but more often most prominently consists of **the enhancement and adaptation of existing software solutions** and/or **the development of support offerings and training materials**, i.e. the realisation of your service components as described in D.Ini.3. They should be extended within the NFDI for widest possible use by the services of the consortia (including e.g. user group-specific adaptations, templates, customisation, metadata integration).
 - If new software is developed, TA1 can support technical design decisions in the development of digital services.
 - For the development of training materials, the **Base4NFDI Training Task Force** can support you.
- All output of a service should be published as open as possible:
 - **Software** developed for your service must be **licensed** under an open and ideally permissive license, like [MIT](#), [Apache 2.0](#) or the [BSD 3-clause license](#)³. The storage of your software in a standardised and accessible repository⁴ is highly recommended.
 - **Other outputs** of a service like guides and training materials must be **licensed** conformant with the principles set forth in the [Open Definition](#), e.g. with the [Creative Commons](#) license [CC-BY 4.0](#). The storage of your output in a standardised and accessible repository is also highly appreciated.
- The **TA1 team** can support the development of the service by offering events if deemed necessary (e.g. workshops, hackathons, or community meetings, focusing on quality, sustainability and others).
- The basic service in the Initialisation Phase must be **provided as a prototype**. Note that if you develop software, then for completion of the Initialisation Phase the prototype has to be compliant with a [Technology Readiness Level](#) of TRL 5-6 (minimum). Please assess the TRL by yourself and add a description, which criteria and methods you used, e.g. for defining a TRL for several components of your service, which might not all have the same maturity.

Deliverable D.Ini.5 Piloting and Testing

- At the end of Initialisation, your service must be integrated into two or three consortia, as a **proof of concept** and **tested with a selected (small) group of users** (end-users or service providers). If you are **not** able to integrate your service into at least two consortia, then describe the reasons for this in your report.
- The aim of the piloting and testing phase is to **demonstrate the general applicability** of the basic service and to get an initial **response from the community** (in-depth user testing is reserved for the Integration Phase).
 - Piloting and user testing should be standardised and harmonised.

³ The [Licensing Assistant from the European Commission](#) can help you to find an appropriate license. We recommend setting the filters 'permissive' and 'strong community'.

⁴ In [re3data](#) you can search for repositories for all types of output (e.g. software, data and documents).

- Note that Task Area 4 can provide training for user testing as early as appropriate.
- It goes along with the development of guidelines, templates and training materials depending on the target audience.
- The **TA1 team** supports piloting and testing by providing a [Toolkit for Harmonizing Piloting and Testing Strategies](#).
For onboarding pilot users or administrators and community IT staff, training material will be required. The **Base4NFDI Training Task Force** can support you in identifying target groups, learning goals and continuously developing training materials.
Service Stewards can assist you by establishing links with the consortia and their user bases.
The **TA1 team** can also support piloting and testing by offering events (e.g. workshops or community meetings). Events at this stage can encourage dialogue between existing and new service providers and promote service dissemination.

Deliverable D.Ini.6 Presentation to the Section and as a Short Overview

- With the end of the Initialisation Phase, you must give a **presentation of your results to the NFDI section** that initiated your service. This is mandatory to complete your Initialisation Phase. Please contact the spokesperson for this NFDI section in good time so that your presentation can be scheduled for the meeting shortly before the end of your Initialisation Phase.
- Additionally, you must submit a **short report on the results** of your Basic Service (1 page), following the [Guidelines for a Short Overview of a Basic Service at the End of the Initialisation Phase](#). This short report will be published as a news item on the Base4NFDI website. You can also choose to publish your results e.g. as a blog post on your website.
- Both items have to be completed no later than **6 weeks after the end of your Initialisation Phase**.

Deliverable D.Ini.7 Participate in Base4NFDI outreach events

- Active participation with a **presentation** of the service
 - at the Base4NFDI User Conference
 - at the Base4NFDI Services Roadshow
 - and as a [NFDI talk](#)
 is mandatory during the Initialisation Phase.

3. Documentation

It is generally **recommended to document all deliverables** of your Initialisation Phase, be they self-defined or part of the mandatory Initialisation Phase deliverables. The documentation of all deliverables must be performed **in the NFDI project management tool [OpenProject](#)**. Their completion will also be tracked in this tool.

The documentation must be up to date, since it is **required for your Integration Phase proposal** six months after the start of your Initialisation Phase: You must hand in reports about the following deliverables:

- Documentation of requirements analysis (D.Ini.1)
- Documentation of software or service evaluation (D.Ini.2)
- Documentation of service design (D.Ini.3)

The reports on these deliverables need to be updated during the Initialisation Phase and must be submitted - together with a short overview of the results - as a final report to the Base4NFDI office and TA3 no later than **six weeks after the end of the Initialisation Phase**.

The complete list of the **final reports** is therefore:

- Documentation of requirements analysis (D.Ini.1)
- Documentation of software or service evaluation (D.Ini.2)
- Documentation of service design (D.Ini.3)
- Short Overview of the results (D.Ini.6)

An export of your documentation in [OpenProject](#) is sufficient as a report. For a more exhaustive summary on how to report in [OpenProject](#), please refer to the [HowTo: Reporting in Initialisation Phase](#). In [OpenProject](#) you can provide both your technical or user documentation (the publicly available part of your service documentation) and any internal/confidential parts; as a link or as text, as you see fit. If you use external documentation for your deliverables, link them to the [OpenProject](#) tasks and make sure that Base4NFDI is granted access.

If you publish your reports, please follow the [Signalisation instructions Base4NFDI](#) and the [Base4NFDI Publication Policy](#). You must acknowledge both Base4NFDI and the funder DFG together with the funding number for basic services 521453681. It is also possible to use the Base4NFDI and DFG logos, which are available for download on this [website](#).

Documentation of the Deliverables

Requirements Analysis (D.Ini.1)

- Provide a summary of requirements from the consortia for a basic service on your specific topic.
- Provide an overview of the expectations formulated by the consortia in the relevant working group on the topic and which part of these expectations the proposed solution fulfils.
 - If applicable, also indicate the methodology used (e.g. survey).

- Define the target group(s) for the service and their use cases. Describe the benefits for each target group.
- The report for this deliverable is planned **3 months** after the start date, but the timeline can be adapted. Please consider that requirements may change over time or new requirements may come up, e.g. during piloting and testing of your prototype. The requirements should be kept up to date.

Evaluation of Existing Software or Services (D.Ini.2)

- Provide an overview of the evaluation of the different aspects (e.g. functionality, performance, security, usability).
- The report for this deliverable is planned **6 months** after the start date.

Service Design (D.Ini.3)

- Document the tools, frameworks, methods and technologies used for the basic service.
 - Explain the rationale for the choice of technology stack/methods/tools.
 - Where appropriate, document the user interface and/or APIs depending on the target audience.
- Describe how the basic service is integrated into the NFDI service landscape.
- The report for this deliverable is planned **6 months** after the start date.
 - As the documentation of the service design could be a starting point for the technical and user documentation of the basic service when it is completed and running, you should already consider a suitable way to host structured, versioned and collaboratively maintained service documentation (e.g. markdown based documentation hosted on GitHub, with a static site generator such as MkDocs or Hugo). Note: This refers to the publicly available part of your service documentation. See also the [Base4NFDI Service Documentation Guide](#).
 - For an overview on what to consider for the documentation, please have a look at our [20 Questions about Service Design](#). To learn more about service design aspects to be addressed in Base4NFDI, take a look into the [Service Design Guide](#).

Short Overview (D.Ini.6)

At the end of the Initialisation Phase, a short overview of the service and the results of the Initialisation Phase must be written. The text must include a brief overview of the service:

- What can the service be used for?
- Who can use it?
- How can it be used?

This short report will be published as a news item on the Base4NFDI website. Alternatively, you can choose your own way of publishing a summary of your basic service, e.g. as PID4NFDI did with their [blog post](#). For more information see the [Guidelines for a Short Overview of a Basic Service at the End of the Initialisation Phase](#).

4. Base4NFDI Deliverables in Initialisation Phase - Recommended Deadlines

Milestone	Deliverable	Type	Description	Recommended Date after start
	D.Ini.1	Report	Documentation of requirements analysis	3M Update when necessary
	D.Ini.2	Report	Documentation of evaluation of existing software and services	6M
	D.Ini.3	Report	Documentation of service design	6M
	D.Ini.4	Service	Service prototype	End of Ini. Phase ⁵
	D.Ini.5	Service	Service piloting and user testing	End of Ini. Phase
M.Ini.1			Service ready for integration	End of Ini. Phase
	D.Ini.6	Presentation and Report	Presentation and short overview about the outcomes of the Initialisation Phase	End of Ini. Phase
	D.Ini.7	Presentation	Talks at Base4NFDI User Conference, the Services Roadshow and an NFDI presentation	End of Ini. Phase

⁵ According to the BASE funding the Initialisation Phase ends after 12 months, but a cost neutral prolongation can be checked and eventually approved by BASE-TA1.